

Original Research Article

Perception of BSN Students of University of Lahore about Nursing Image and their Reasons to join the Nursing Profession: A Cross-sectional Study

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Abstract

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Nursing is a health-care profession dedicated to the care of individuals, families, and communities in order for them to achieve, maintain, or recover a healthy lifestyle. Nurses provide holistic care to people of all ages and different cultures, both healthy and weak, based on the individual's physical, emotional, behavioural, philosophical, social, as well as religious aspects. The main objective is to determine the perception of BSN students of UOL about nursing image and to determine reasons for BSN students of UOL to join the nursing profession. A cross sectional study design was used in Lahore school of Nursing, University of Lahore, Pakistan. Questionnaire distributed among nursing students and data analyzed by SPSS software (version 21). The results show that 75.2% of students have a negative perception and 24.8% have a positive perception of the student about nursing image. The estimated reasons to join the nursing profession in a graph show that 36.3% have bad reasons and 63.7% have good reasons to join the nursing profession. The study concludes that the student's negative perception of the nursing image and majority of the participants join the nursing profession for the purpose of securing a job easily, financial crises and peer pressure but actually they aren't interested in nursing profession. Professional perspective has a significant impact on nursing student development and future nursing reliability. As a result, students are hesitant to take nursing as a career.

Keywords: BSN students, Nursing image, Nursing profession, Perception, Reasons

INTRODUCTION

Nursing is a health-care profession dedicated to the care of individuals, families, and communities in order for them to achieve, maintain, or recover a healthy lifestyle. Nurses provide holistic care to people of all ages and different cultures, both healthy and weak, based on the individual's physical, emotional, behavioural, philoso-

phical, social, as well as religious aspects (Patidar et al., 2016).

The image and social position of nursing, as well as the definition of nursing roles, are global issues that nurses perform. The "personality of a person or thing as viewed by the public" is described as an image. Actual

research from industrialized and developing economies suggests that a negative or poor image is a persistent major issue for the healthcare profession. The inability of the people to understand the role of the nurse, negative representation of nurses in the media, unsafe workplace environment, unhealthy relationships from other health care professionals are some of the causes for nursing's negative image (Gul, 2018).

For the past 100-150-years, the image of nursing has become one of the most important factors affecting the nursing profession. It affects nurses' work productivity, stimulates their intention to leave their job, weakens the nurses stability and finally weakens the establishment of some healthcare systems. As a result, the image of nursing will always be a major concern. Nurses who see the occupation as exciting and who provide benefits for the society and are concerned about what the profession is could be much more effective in changing society's negative stereotypes of the profession. As a result, nurses must recognise the shifts in perceptions related to nursing responsibilities and their possible growth (Yilmaz, 2019).

According to the International Council of Nurses (ICN) 2003, Europe, France and the Netherlands have 13,000 nurse shortages, while Switzerland has 3,000. Nurses in Germany, there are 18,000 nurses shortage. Each year, thousands of people leave public hospitals. Currently, half of all nurses in Canada are women, Who In the next 15 years will retire. There are around 126,000 people in the United States. Furthermore, in the year 2004, the predicted retirements among elderly professional nurses in both the United States and Canada will impede the ability to provide quality care as a sufficient number of nursing schools to teach and graduate enough nurses to meet the future requirements. The nursing schools in the United States, about 125,000 candidates were turned down as they are seen as not qualified to enroll in the program (Oulton, 2015).

Continental views of Nurses show that, in Iran attempting to win public image, have been successful as they are trying to rise beyond the subordinated status that they have inherited over the years. Nursing has been portrayed in early Greek literary writings and poems in a negative way, leading to sentiments of despair, helplessness, and confusion regarding identity and self-identification. According to Iranian studies, nursing has a bad social image and low social status in Iran, which contributes to nurses' opinions that their work is not valued or respected. Despite the fact that some research has been done on nurses' social image around the world, there is a lack of information on how Iranian nurses view their social image. As a result, the focus of this research, which is the first of its kind in Iran on nursing image, was to explain Iranian nurses' perceptions on elements impacting their nursing image

(Varaei et al., 2016).

Throughout the history of Pakistan, the image of nursing has changed and evolved, and the upwards image of nursing has improved dramatically in the last 50 years. The development of nursing students is impacted by their professional perspective and future nursing reliability. In each of Pakistan's four provinces, 13132 nurses are trained each year. The ratio is one nurse for every 3175 (1:3175) people, which falls far short of the required ratio. This shortfall is due to the fact that nursing workforce production has been a neglected aspect in Pakistan (Manzoor, 2017).

Nursing is viewed as a female-dominated career with a social status. As a result, students are hesitant to take nursing as a career. As a result, few men find jobs in this field. According to the current statistics, the number of male medical students in Canada is only 9.7%, while it is around 9% in the United States. In Turkey, there is no data on the number of male nurses. However, Turkey's new Nursing Law, which went into force in January 2007, demands for the gender disparity to be closed (Herdman and Badir, 2018).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess the Perception of BSN students about Nursing image and their reasons for joining the nursing profession.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- I. To determine the Perception of BSN students of UOL about nursing image.
- II. To determine reasons for BSN students of UOL to join the nursing profession.

Problem Statement

It is a known fact that most of the paramedical students join nursing because of their financial crises and peer pressure. They join the nursing profession because it is convenient and less expensive. But while searching the researcher found that few studies in which it is mentioned that in advance world student's desirable to join the nursing profession because there is remarkable advancement in the nursing profession. The roots of the nursing profession are spreading day by day. The advancement in the nursing profession also positively influences the image of nursing. That's why the researcher wants to explore it further and wants to work on this particular conflict.

Conceptual and Operational definition

Operational Definition

Perception about nursing image

"Perception is an individual psychological quality in which individuals perceive information, organize it, interpret it, and make judgments." It is how the profession is perceived by others, including the public at large. The most important point is that nurses' image can impact them, just as nurses may feel miserable or less beneficial if others perceive them negatively". Response of participants in "Yes" scored as 1 and in "No" scored as 0. The possible maximum score is =24.

Good Perception = > 70% = > 16.8

Poor Perception = < 70% = < 16.8

Reasons to join nursing profession

"Nursing is a profession in which health care providers facilitate individual communities and families to attain maximum levels of health". Response of participants in "Yes" scored as 1 and in "No" scored as 0.

The possible maximum score is =10.

Good response to join nursing profession = >80% => 8

Bad response to join nursing profession = < 80% = < 8

Conceptual definition

Perception

"Perception can be defined as the selecting, receiving, organizing, and interpreting data from the external environment in order to make it valuable to you." "Decisions and actions are the result of this influx of significant knowledge." (Joseph Reitz, 1993)

Nursing image

"The image of a nurse is extremely significant in the nursing profession. How the general population see the nursing profession. The public's perception of nursing has an effect on student hiring, financing for nursing research and education, interrelations with health-care management and other health-care staff, government entities, and lawmakers at all levels of government, and finally, the organization's self-identity." (Aunguroch, et al., 2018)

Significance of the study

After completion of this research, the participants of

nursing students will get the perception of nursing image. And this will help them to improve their nursing perception about nursing image. This will also help to improve their knowledge and awareness about the nursing profession and the image. The research study will serve as the understanding for researchers about perception of BSN students about nursing image. Hence, the researcher who recommends to policy makers and the public as well as the nurses about knowledge and awareness about the nursing profession, explains its importance in the health care system.

Study Gap

Best of researcher knowledge it is found that there has been not sufficient work done in the nursing profession and image (especially in Pakistan). There is so much research work done on nursing image but while searching for relevant articles the researcher did not find any recent research work on nursing image in Pakistan. Most students join the nursing profession just because it is convenient to take admission in it, not because it is a helping profession. So the researcher was influenced and ambitious to work on this area so that the attitude towards the image of the nursing profession can be enhanced.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study design: The study design used in this study is the Cross-sectional Study Design.

Study site: This study was conducted among BSN students in the University of Lahore.

Study setting: Data will be conducted in BSN nursing students of LSN department from University Of Lahore.

Study Population

Study population consists of the population from which we gather the information. The researcher study population is the students of BSN from the department of LSN university of Lahore. We take this population because we need to check the student's perception regarding the nursing profession and image.

Sample size

Sample size calculated as 157.

Considering, $p=0.5$, 95% of confidence, and least 5+-, precision. A 95% of confidence level gives us Z value of 1.96, per the normal tables, using Cochran's formula

$$[(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)] / (0.05)^2 = 385$$

Modifying the above sample size for a smaller population.

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

Here n_0 is Cochran's sample size recommendation, N is the population size, and n is the new, adjusted sample. Our target population $N=264$ so, we could calculate as:
 $385 / (1 + (384/264)) = 157$

Sampling Strategy

This study will be accomplished using a non-probability convenient sampling technique used in data collection.

Inclusion criteria

- I. In this study the BSN students of University Of Lahore will be included.
- II. All Those participants who are willing to participate and sign the consent will be included in this study.
- III. Both male and female students were included.

Exclusion criteria

- I. Students of Master of Science in nursing (MSN) and post RN will be excluded.
- II. All other departments of UOL other than LSN will be excluded.

Research tool

In this research a self-administered questionnaire adopted from the article to obtain data from the participants will be used to measure the independent variables perception and Dependent variables nursing image about nursing profession.

Data Collection plan

The questionnaire will be distributed among nursing students of University Of Lahore and this questionnaire consists of many questions about perception of BSN students of UOL about nursing image and their reasons to join the nursing profession. Close ended questions will be used. The participants will be assured that their personal information will be kept confidential.

Data Analysis

The data will be analysed on SPSS version 21 and then results will be shown in the charts, tables and figures.

Ethical Considerations

All information of the participants was protected by complete confidentiality. Permission was taken from the students and consent form was signed before collecting the data from the participants. All of the work done by researchers was permitted and fully granted by university authorities as well as each participant of the study. While conducting the research, the ethical approval was obtained of The University of Lahore established rules and regulations, and the interests of the research participants were respected. The subjects were informed that there was no disadvantage of the study. We will do everything possible to keep your information private. Your identity will not be exposed in any study-related publications.

RESULTS

Demographics

Data collected from the BSN students of university of Lahore to assess "The Perception of BSN students of university of Lahore about Nursing image and their reasons to join the nursing profession". A cross sectional study interviewed 157 participants from the University of Lahore. The response of the survey was 100%, the age range of 18 to 25 years old adolescents. The members who participated in age were also participated in gender and academic year. The data analysis consists of two parts, first part of demographic data and second part include perception 24 questionnaire and third part contain reasons 10 questionnaire. Table 1 Shows the demographic characteristics of BSN nursing students and table 1 shows that there were 157 participants of the study, 47 participants were under the age of 18-20 years old, 94 were between 21-24 years and only 16 participants more than 25 years old. 44 participants were males and 113 were females. 35 participants were from 1st year, 38 participants from 2nd year, 40 participants from 3rd year, and 44 participants from 4th year.

Table 2 indicates the perception questions and the basic information of the students regarding the perception of BSN students about nursing image. Every question response was scored "Yes", and "No". The mean number of the knowledge questions is 13%.

Table 3 shows the reasons for the students to join the nursing profession. Mean number of total reason questions is 5.9%.

Table 1. Demographic characteristic of the participants

	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-20 years	47	29.9
	21-24 years	94	59.9
	More than 25 years	16	10.2
	Total	157	100
Gender	Male	44	28
	Female	113	72
	Total	157	100
Academic year	1 st year	35	22.3
	2 nd year	38	24.2
	3 rd year	40	25.5
	4 th year	44	28.0
	Total	157	100

Table 2. Frequency and percentage of perception of the students about nursing image

Sr#	Questions	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
1.	Do you have a nurse in your family?	93 (59.2%)	64 (40.8%)
2.	Do you know the nursing profession prior to joining the university?	95 (60.5%)	62 (39.5%)
3.	Knowing the profession prior to university?	95 (60.5%)	62 (39.5%)
4.	Do you have the satisfaction of choosing the nursing profession?	63 (40.1%)	94 (59.9%)
5.	Do you have other professional requests?	65 (41.1%)	92 (58.6%)
6.	Do you respect the profession of nursing as much as the Profession of medicine?	102 (65.0%)	55 (35.0%)
7.	Do you believe nursing is a respectful profession?	68 (43.3%)	89 (56.7%)
8.	Do you believe nursing is only Women's profession?	94 (59.9%)	63 (40.1%)
9.	Do you think nursing is an extremely hard profession that does not receive enough appreciation?	86 (54.8%)	71 (45.2%)
10.	Nursing is an independent profession by which nurses make decisions for themselves.	87 (55.4%)	70 (44.6%)
11.	Do you believe nurses are given a chance to use their own initiative in their work?	87 (55.4%)	70 (44.6%)
12.	Nurses waste a lot of time being busy doing nothing.	103 (65.6%)	54 (34.4%)
13.	Would you like your child to be a nurse?	103 (65.6%)	54 (34.4%)
14.	Caring profession in which ethical standards of care are maintained.	111 (70.7%)	46 (29.3%)
15.	Do you think nursing is actually equal to other professions?	71 (45.2%)	86 (54.8%)
16.	Do you believe nursing is a significant in a patient's recovery?	94 (59.9%)	63 (40.1%)
17.	Nursing helps in promotion of health and prevention of diseases.	101 (64.3%)	56 (35.7%)
18.	Nurses obey doctors' orders without questioning them.	86 (54.8%)	71 (45.2%)
19.	Do you think patients trust the nurse's clinical evaluation of your health?	94 (59.9%)	63 (40.1%)

Table 2. Continue

20.	Do you feel that patient care needs are met by nurses?	99 (63.1%)	58 (36.9%)
21.	Do you think patients trust the nurse's competencies in clinical practice?	95 (60.5%)	62 (39.5%)
22.	Do you think the nurse's gestures are pleasant?	79 (50.3%)	78 (49.7%)
23.	Throughout the period of patient hospitalization, Do you think the nurse's caring; gesture and body language are human?	79 (50.3%)	78 (49.7%)
24.	Did the nurse demonstrate availability of time for care?	87 (55.4%)	70 (44.6%)

Table 3. Frequency and percentage of reasons to join nursing profession

Sr#	Questions	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
1.	Is nursing an opportunity to make a real difference in people's lives?	66 (42.0%)	91 (58.0%)
2.	Nursing profession has ample job opportunities.	73 (46.5%)	84 (53.5%)
3.	Nursing profession is a rewarding and fulfilling career path.	98 (62.4%)	59 (37.6%)
4.	Nursing has a significant opportunity for Interprofessional collaboration among a variety of health care disciplines.	104 (66.2%)	53 (33.8%)
5.	Nursing offers a high degree of job satisfaction.	119 (75.8%)	38 (24.2%)
6.	A nursing Employment choice is wide and varies.	104 (66.2%)	53 (33.8%)
7.	Nursing do a full work or a part time and varying shifts.	95 (60.5%)	62 (39.5%)
8.	Nursing profession provides freedom to work in other countries.	95 (60.5%)	62 (39.5%)
9.	Nurses receive high earning potential.	87 (55.4%)	70 (44.6%)
10.	Nursing is a high demand profession.	87 (55.4%)	70 (44.6%)

Table 4. Overall Perception of the participants

	Frequency	Percentage
Good Perception of the participants	39	24.8%
Poor Perception of the participants	118	75.2%

Figure 1. Total perception

Table 5. Overall Reasons to join nursing profession of the participants

	Frequency	Percentage
Good Reasons of the participants	57	36.3%
Bad Reasons of the participants	100	63.7%

Figure 2. Reasons to join nursing profession

The figure 1 shows that the overall perception was poor (75.2%) and Good perception of the participants is (24.8%).

The figure shows that the overall reasons to join nursing profession was bad (63.7%) and Good reasons of the participants is (36.3%).

DISCUSSION

The frequency and percentages of nurses' perceptions of

nursing image in many domains are shown below. In the area of nature of job satisfaction, 98.6 percent of nurses said that one of their responsibilities as nurses was to provide satisfaction during times of helplessness, and 92.7 percent said they met many uncomfortable situations as nurses (Faghihzadeh, 2012). According to my findings, in table 2 question 20, "Do you feel that patient care needs are met by nurses" 63% of respondents agreed that the nurses comforted the patients at the time of their needs.

According to data presented in table (2), more than

the majority of the study subjects enrolled in the School of Nursing because of the variety of job options available (54.4 %). Nonetheless, over majority of them (50.2 %) did so as a result of their secondary education grade. The reasons for 44.6% and 41.7 % of them, however, were a complicated career (economic reason) and their families' counsel. The desire to help others, on the other hand, was the motivation for 31.6 percent of the participants (Abd El Rahman and Abou Shousha, 2013). In my statistical findings in table no (3) question no (1) shows that the respondents said "yes" 42% and "no" 58% these results showed that nursing is not just the career opportunity it is more than the make a real difference in people's lives.

In relation to the findings, it is possible to conclude that high school student nurses have a more unfavorable perception of nurses than university nursing students. According to one research, Turkish society has a negative perception of the healthcare profession, and seniors nursing students agreed with this perception. According to a research conducted to determine the impressions of university students who are enrolled in other fields, 62 percent of students answered "poor" to the question "what is the image of nursing in society?" and usually responded unfavorable questions about nursing (Elilbol and Seren, 2017). Statistics show that "Do you know the nursing profession prior to joining the university" 60% respondents respond as "yes". It has been proven that having a favorable perspective and attitude toward a career is a necessary reason for choosing a career, gaining proficiency in a profession, and maintaining a fruitful work life. In this survey, it was discovered that the majority of students knew about the profession before starting school, and that the half of majority had positive sentiments regarding nursing.

In the study's 'nurse concept' category, male students indicated dissatisfaction with the profession's name. Female learners, on the other hand, had no negative feelings about the situation. Some studies have found that male students are uncomfortable with the program's name because nurse is a Turkish word that means "sister" and is linked with women (Bahçecik and Alpar, 2019). Results of my study shows in table no 3 that the strength of male participants is less than female. Males who responded to my study were 28% and females were 72%. This suggests that positive exposure could influence male career selections. Most male students claimed nursing signified 'job guarantee' in the 'choosing' section. Females were less affected by this element; their decisions are mostly influenced by the expectations and advice of their family members and educators.

The average score for American students that had a healthcare professional in their home was greater than for all those who had not. Students who choose clinical experience without prior knowledge of the profession or with social preconceptions cannot be supposed to have a

realistic perspective of the profession when they begin university. After receiving theoretical and practical education, students' perceptions of the profession can change for the good or for the worse. Statistical analysis of my study shows in the table no 4 question no 1" Do you have a nurse in your family" 59% respond as yes and 40 % says no. Because they do not like and do not adopt their career, they encounter problems including being restless at work, working inefficiently, and making a mistake. These issues have a negative impact on the profession's acceptability in society. Similarly, in this study, the average score was greater for students who willingly picked the nursing profession, did not want to abandon it, and intended to work in a hospital after graduation.

CONCLUSION

From the findings, several conclusions were arrived at. My results suggested that the perceptions of the students about nursing image is negative 56% (Estimated percentage was >70%) and the reasons to join nursing profession was also negative 59% (Estimated percentage was >70%). The study concludes that the student's negative perception of the nursing image and majority of the participants join the nursing profession for the purpose of securing a job easily, financial crises and peer pressure but actually they aren't interested in nursing profession. The public's inability to comprehend the job of the nurse, bad media portrayals of nurses, an unsafe workplace environment, and unhealthy relationships with other health-care professionals are some of the factors that contribute to nursing's negative image. Professional perspective has a significant impact on nursing student development and future nursing reliability. As a result, students are hesitant to take nursing as a career.

RECOMMENDATION

Current study was conducted to the perception of BSN students of the University of Lahore about nursing image and their reasons to join nursing profession. This study recommendation is following in the future are:

- I. Improve the professional behaviour of nursing students through the conduct of training programs and make them aware of nursing image.
- II. Nursing students must be encouraged to begin their careers at the bedside nurse, and the organization and authorities must be prepared in preventing nursing skills shortage.
- III. Education should be provided to the schools and college students about the nursing profession and their image and they add to the curriculum learning.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study found many limitations; firstly this is my first effort to write and conduct research study. Secondly, the time duration was very short. The study sample size of my research should be large and the data collection faced lots of problems and the respondents of the study were not cooperative and had a very careless attitude to fill the questionnaire. Some of the students refused to fill my questionnaire and they said they don't have time to fill this question paper. Participants of the study have no idea about the value and importance of the questionnaire.

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